

THE STUDY OF DISEASES OF THE UTERUS OF CATS USING A PYROMETER AND THE CAUSES OF ITS OCCURRENCE

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ABSTRACT

The article provides an overview of inflammatory uterine disease occurring in pedigreed cats and wild stray cats bred in apartments of urban and rural populations, pays attention to small animals in veterinary industries, briefly describes the causes of the disease, their types, causes, complications, as well as treatment and prevention measures.

The relevance of the topic. In recent years, most urban and rural residents of the world have bred purebred cats in households more often than other pets. Because cats are affectionate and devoted animals, they cheer people up, normalize the nervous system in stressful situations. The beauty of the body structure, the shine of the coat differs from other animals in its softness, variety, grace, softness and brightness. There are about 60 standardized cat breeds in the world, and the cat family includes about 35 species. Their number increases by 4-5% annually. In veterinary medicine, it is important to improve the health of small animals, protect against various diseases, prevent and treat, as well as preserve their lives. In recent years, in our country, attention to small animals in the branches of the veterinary sphere has been growing from year to year. Most of these animals are fur-bearing animals. As for cats from small

animals in this regard, they are considered harmless animals. Currently, there are about 600 million domestic cats in the world, recognized and listed by various felinological organizations. About 200 breeds have been bred, from long-haired (Persian) to tailless (sphinxes). However, neglected cats roaming the streets of cities, representing epidemiological and epizootological danger, and cats bred in residents' apartments, can pose a danger to human health as a result of infection with various infectious and invasive diseases if their population is not controlled, not regulated. In addition, besides to non-communicable diseases, there are many types of diseases of the uterus (endometritis, pyometra, hematometer, hydrometer, etc.). With early detection of the disease, treatment becomes possible. However, some diseases in the acute stage (pyometra) are not treatable. . In veterinary practice, cats with such a

(pyometra) disease can save lives only surgically. Due to the fact that there are practically no veterinary clinics in all regions of our republic, the conditions for preserving the life of these animals are insufficient. Therefore, currently an urgent problem is the improvement of treatment technology, preventive measures for diseases of the reproductive organ of cats.

The degree of knowledge on the scale of the problem. There are a number of foreign scientists in the world on this problem, such as Shamraevsky S. M., 1950; Dolinsky S.Ya. and-AUTHOR, 1980; Khramov Y.V., et al., 1998; 1962; Dobby A. K., 1969; Friedman I., 1973; Honig W. M., 1975; Mann W., Klippel Ch., 1977; Kokurichev P.I., 1994; Stepanenko M.V., 1998; Vesnina V.N., 2000; Baranov O.B., 2001; Arnold S. 1989. Georgievsky V.I., 1990; Karpov V.A., 1990; Khramov Yu.V. et al., 1998; Stepanenko M.V., 1998; Biorg V., 1999; Tilly L., Smith F., 2001. According to the clinical signs of feline diseases in the republic and on the treatment and prevention of diseases and methods of their treatment, B.V.Narziev, J.I. Yulchiev was studied. However, in our country, scientific research is not conducted enough on diseases of the uterus of cats and their spread, identification of factors provoking the disease, features of the course of the disease, development of measures for their treatment and prevention, as well as their introduction into practice.

Research methods. Inflammation of cat tags is called pyometra by veterinarians. The disease occurs mainly in adult cats older than 5 years old who have not been sterilized. Cats blush because of inflammation of the uterus, which subsequently leads to suppuration. As a result, the uterus and its neck swell and the

canal becomes clogged. As a result, pus begins to accumulate inside, and not flow out. Of course, this situation is dangerous for the animal. In most cases, the animal causes the deposition of pus inside the uterus as a result of improper treatment of the host or doctors with hormone, antibiotics and other drugs. If the disease is not diagnosed correctly and not treated in time, then the pus accumulated in the uterus begins to be absorbed by the cells into the blood and the animal's condition begins to deteriorate. The volume of pus can reach several liters in large animals. The accumulation of pus in the uterus is accompanied by severe toxicosis, increased thirst and often high fever. Most often, pyometra occurs 4-6 weeks after Purulent metritis. As a result of this disease, the animal has an increased risk of developing peritonitis, uterine perforation and death. As a result of studying the causes of the disease, we have identified the following data. After analyzing this situation, we made certain conclusions about the causes of the disease. They are as follows:

- infection;
- hormonal disorders;
- regular use of hormonal agents (for example, during estrus);
- caused by complicated labor;
- retention of a dead fetus in the uterus;
- have sex with different cats;

Symptoms of the disease include: cats have problems such as restless behavior, loss of appetite, cramps as a result of abdominal pain, often weakness and incontinence, and other symptoms.

Conclusion. It will be possible to identify and cure the onset of pyometra in cats at an early stage using modern methods using ultrasound machines. If the disease progressed, the uterus swelled, bloody pus

accumulated, disorders in the tissues were observed, it would be possible to save the animal's life only surgically. In other difficult situations, the animal dies.

Therefore, it is always advisable to monitor animals if preventive measures are often carried out to prevent diseases and this will save the lives of animals.

References:

1. Lazarev N.V. Reproduction of diseases in animals for experimental therapeutic research. - M.: "Medgiz", 1954. - 391 p.
2. Kozins G.I., Makarov V.A. Investigation of the blood system in clinical practice. - M.: Triad-x, 1997. - 480 p.
3. Kokurichev P.I., Domnin B.G., Kokurichev M.P. Pathological anatomy of farm animals. - M.: "Agropromizdat", 1994. - 212 p.
4. Kolushov N.P. Stopping bleeding after castration of animals // Veterinary medicine. - 1972. - No. 5. - pp. 74-75.
5. Shebits H., Brass V. Operative surgery of dogs and cats / Translated from English - M.: LLC "AQUARIUM LTD", 2001. -512.